

which is separable from β -pinene only with great difficulty. A Darmois diagram of the various fractions shows, however, that anomalous rotatory dispersion in the near ultraviolet still remains a characteristic of β -pinene. This conclusion is supported by Raman effect data of the various fractions obtained.

3. The anomalous rotatory dispersion of β -pinene is not due to Cotton-effect because there is no evidence of any absorption in the region of the anomaly. It must, therefore, be due to a superposition effect caused by a second rotation of opposite sign and having a different dispersion.

4. This second rotation cannot be attributed to the 'induced dissymmetry' of the semicyclic double bond because camphene which is also similarly constituted has been shown in a previous work to possess normal dispersion.

DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received June 4, 1935.

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part IV.
5-Bromonarcotine, 5-Bromocotarnine, 5-Bromohydro-
cotarnine and 5-Bromonarceine and their Derivatives.

BY B. B. DEY AND T. K. SRINIVASAN.

The only references to literature about bromocotarnine and bromohydrocotarnine are to be found in two papers by Wright (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, **32**, 525) and by Heimann (Dissertation, Marburg, 1892, p. 15; also Small, "Chemistry of the Opium Alkaloids," 1932, pp. 68, 70, 98). Bromonarcotine and bromonarceine do not appear to have been prepared before.

Wright examined in detail the action of bromine water on a solution of hydrocotarnine in hydrobromic acid. He obtained a bromohydrocotarnine (m.p. 76°), and a perbromide of the latter which was supposed to decompose on standing in the presence of water into bromocotarnine and hydrobromic acid. As it seemed very remarkable that hydrocotarnine could be so easily oxidised to cotarnine by simple treatment with bromine water, we repeated this work with care, but although we readily obtained bromohydrocotarnine and the perbromide in a pure condition, we have been unable to confirm Wright's observation that bromocotarnine was formed in this reaction. The low melting point recorded by Wright (100° instead of 135°) also indicates the bromocotarnine, if obtained at all, having been very impure. Heimann (*loc. cit.*) prepared bromocotarnine by the action of bromine water on a solution of cotarnine hydrochloride, the precipitated perbromide being reduced with H₂S.

The bromination of narcotine in cold acid solution proceeds smoothly and leads to the formation of almost the theoretical quantity of 5-bromonarcotine perbromide hydrobromide which is fairly stable and crystallises from alcohol in light yellow needles, (m.p. 220° decomp.). The reduction of the latter in the usual way gives 5-bromonarcotine crystallising in colourless needles (m. p. 176°). Oxidation of the latter with nitric acid gave almost a theoretical yield of 5-bromocotarnine (yellowish white needles, m. p. 135°, identical with the product obtained from cotarnine by direct bromination) and opianic acid. Similarly, 5-bromonarceine crystallising in silky needles (m. p. 193°) was readily obtained from the bromonarcotine by steaming a mixture of the latter with methyl-*p*-toluene sulphonate and sodium hydroxide (Rodionov, *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1926, 39, 305). The position of the bromine atom in all these derivatives has been settled by the conversion of 5-bromocotarnine through exhaustive methylation into 5-bromocotarnone and oxidation of the latter into 5-bromocotarnolactone, and finally into 5-bromocotarnic acid. A further argument in support of this position being assigned to the bromine atom in these derivatives is derived from the observation that neither 5-bromocotarnine nor 5-bromonarcotine condenses with formaldehyde which is known to attack only the 5 position in these bases, when free. Our results are summarised in the scheme given on the next page.

The formulæ of most of the compounds described in this paper may be referred to either of the two following types :

EXPERIMENTAL.

5-Bromonarcotine.—Finely powdered narcotine (5 g.) was dissolved in 20 c. c. of water containing 2 c. c. of 48% HBr, the solution cooled in ice and saturated bromine water added with constant stirring until the yellowish white precipitate which redissolved on shaking, became permanent. The turbid solution was then treated with sulphuretted hydrogen, the solution filtered from any precipitated sulphur and the clear solution basified with ammonia. The bromonarcotine was filtered after an hour, washed with water and dried on a porous plate and crystallised from 90% alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 176°, yield 5.5 g. [Found (in sample dried at 100°): C, 53.51; H, 4.53; Br, 15.84. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N \cdot Br$ requires C, 53.65; H, 4.47; Br, 16.26 per cent]. 1.13 G. of the substance in 25 c. c. of chloroform solution gave in a 2 dm. tube a rotation of -4.29° ; $[\alpha]_D^{30} = -95^\circ$. In dilute mineral acids the substance goes into solution, but not immediately. The base is difficultly soluble in alcohol but dissolves easily in acetone and chloroform. It imparts a carmine-red colour to concentrated sulphuric acid, whereas narcotine gives only a yellow colour. The hydrochloride and hydrobromide are sparingly soluble and separate from solutions of the base in moderately strong acids.

The *hydrochloride* forms a white crystalline powder, m. p. 120°. [Found (on heating at 110° over P_2O_5 at 5 mm.): Cl(HCl), 6.61; H_2O , 3.06. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N \cdot Br, HCl, H_2O$ requires Cl(HCl), 6.49; H_2O , 3.29 per cent].

The *hydrobromide* formed a similar powder melting at 168°. [Found: Br(HBr), 13.67; H_2O , 3.33. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7N \cdot Br, HBr, H_2O$ requires Br(HBr), 13.53; H_2O , 3.04 per cent].

The *perbromide hydrobromide*.—Narcotine (0.5 g.) was dissolved in dilute HBr and saturated bromine water slowly added with continuous stirring until precipitation was complete. The precipitate was collected at once, washed rapidly with cold water, dried and crystallised from hot 90% alcohol as fine yellow needles darkening at 210° and melting at 220° (decomp.); the pure product weighed 0.7 g. On passing H_2S through a suspension of the perbromide in water and basifying the clear solution with ammonia, 5-bromonarcotine, m. p. 176°, was recovered completely. Three out of the 4 bromine atoms in the perbromide were estimated by warming the substance

with dilute caustic soda, acidifying with nitric acid and precipitating the bromide with silver nitrate. [Found: Br, 33.05. $C_{22}H_{22}O_7NBr_3$, HBr requires (for 3 atoms of Br,) Br, 32.74 per cent].

The *platinichloride* was thrown down as a pale yellow granular powder. [Found: Pt, 13.7. $(C_{22}H_{22}O_7NBr, HCl)_2 PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 14.0 per cent].

The *picrate* crystallises from alcohol in yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 197°. (Found: C, 46.2; H, 4.01. $C_{28}H_{25}O_{14}N_4Br$ requires C, 46.6; H, 3.46 per cent).

The *methiodide*, prepared by heating the components in a pressure bottle at 100° for 3 hours and crystallising the dark brown mass twice from hot dilute alcohol (charcoal), formed stout colourless needles, m. p. 220°. [Found (in a sample dried at 110° in vacuum): C, 43.39; H, 4.45. $C_{22}H_{25}O_7NBrI$ requires C, 43.53; H, 3.94 per cent].

5-Bromocotarnine. (a) *By oxidation of bromonarcotine.*—Nitric acid (*d* 1.4, 20 c. c.) was diluted with water (50 c. c.), the acid warmed to 49° and finely powdered bromonarcotine (10 g.) added in small quantities with continuous stirring, the whole process requiring about an hour. The clear yellow solution was transferred to a stoppered bottle, shaken mechanically for half an hour and then left overnight in a large vacuum jar containing water at about 50°. The filtered solution was cooled in ice, a strong solution of caustic soda added gradually with stirring and the precipitated bromocotarnine washed and dried on a plate; yellowish white powder, m. p. 129-30°, weighing nearly 6 g. One crystallisation from alcohol gave pure white needles, m. p. 135°. It is sparingly soluble in cold alcohol but dissolves readily in hot alcohol, acetone and chloroform. [Found (in sample dried in vacuum over KOH): C, 45.0; H, 4.41. $C_{12}H_{14}O_4N Br$ requires C, 45.56; H, 4.43 per cent]. The *hydrochloride*, obtained by evaporating the acid solution over H_2SO_4 in vacuum, was very soluble in water, m. p. 170° (decomp.).

(b) *By bromination of cotarnine.*—Cotarnine (5 g.) dissolved in dilute HBr, was treated with excess of saturated bromine water (400 c. c.) till there was no further precipitation. The orange-red precipitate was filtered, washed and suspended in water and decomposed by H_2S . The precipitate obtained by basifying the clear

solution with caustic soda, crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles, m. p. 135°, yield 3.4 g.

The method of preparing bromocotarnine by oxidation of bromonarcotine is much to be preferred to the latter method both on account of the simplicity of the process and the improved yield of the product.

The *perbromide hydrobromide* was prepared from the orange-red precipitate obtained above by drying and crystallising from hot alcohol as beautiful orange-red needles, m. p. 200° (decomp.). [Found (in material dried in vacuum at room temperature): C, 26.33; H, 2.72. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N Br_3, HBr$ requires C, 26.71; H, 2.41 per cent]. The available bromine in the perbromide was also estimated as follows:— A weighed amount was dissolved in methanol and treated with excess of potassium iodide solution followed by dilute H_2SO_4 , the liberated iodine being titrated at once against standard thiosulphate. (Found: available Br, 29.49. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3N Br_3, HBr$ requires Br, 29.68 per cent).

The *picrate* crystallises from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 171°.

The *platinichloride* came down as a pale yellow crystalline powder. [Found: Pt, 19.63. $(C_{12}H_{12}O_3N Br, HCl)_2 PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 19.4 per cent].

5-Bromocotarnomethine methiodide, prepared by heating the components under pressure in the usual manner, crystallised from hot water in stout straw-yellow needles, m.p. 179°, yield quantitative. (Found: C, 35.22; H, 4.05. $C_{14}H_{19}O_4N Br I$ requires C, 35.59; H, 4.02 per cent).

Benzoyl-5-bromocotarnine (I, $R=CO\cdot Ph$) was prepared by rubbing in a mortar a suspension of bromocotarnine (1 g.) in excess of dilute alkali with benzoyl chloride (10 drops) until the oil solidified completely. Crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave short colourless prisms, m.p. 103°. (Found: C, 53.91; H, 4.63. $C_{19}H_{18}O_5NBr$ requires C, 54.28; H, 4.28 per cent).

5-Bromocotarnine oxime hydrochloride separated as yellow crystals on warming an alcoholic solution of bromocotarnine with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and sodium acetate and then diluting it with water. Crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave colourless

needles, m.p. 169°. The free *oxime* was obtained by basifying the aqueous solution with ammonia and crystallising it from alcohol as needles, m.p. 138°. (Found: C, 43.32; H, 4.21. $C_{12}H_{15}O_4N_2Br$ requires C, 43.50; H, 4.53 per cent).

5-Bromocotarnone.

A mixture of the cotarnometline methiodide (2 g.) and caustic soda (10 %, 20 c.c.) was distilled in steam till the distillate was neutral. A small part of the bromocotarnone volatilised with the steam and condensed in the receiver as white flakes; the major portion remained in the flask and separated as a dark amorphous mass on cooling. Two crystallisations from very dilute alcohol (charcoal) gave a mass of light colourless needles, m.p. 104°. (Found: C, 46.65; H, 3.11. $C_{11}H_9O_4Br$ requires C, 46.31; H, 3.15 per cent).

5-Bromocotarnomethylphenyl urea (I, $R = CO \cdot NH \cdot Ph$).—5-Bromocotarnine (1 g.), suspended in benzene (10 c.c.) was treated with a few drops of phenyl isocyanate. The reaction was vigorous and crystals of the urea derivative separated almost immediately, m.p. 160°. It is insoluble in dilute acids. (Found: C, 53.1; H, 4.5; N, 6.1. $C_{19}H_{19}O_5N_2Br$ requires C, 52.42; H, 4.36; N, 6.43 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared in the usual way. It crystallised in flat shining needles, m.p. 168-69°. (Found: N, 9.66. $C_{19}H_{20}O_5N_3Br$ requires N, 9.34 per cent).

Anhydrobromocotarnino-nitromethane (II, $R = CH_2 \cdot NO_2$).—A warm alcoholic solution of bromocotarnine (1 g.) was mixed with nitromethane (12 drops) and heated just to boiling and allowed to stand. The product separated out on cooling as silky colourless needles which were recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 148°, yield quantitative. (Found: C, 43.05; H, 4.31. $C_{13}H_{15}O_5N_2Br$ requires C, 43.45; H, 4.17 per cent). It yields a sparingly soluble hydrochloride crystallising in prisms, m.p. 166°.

N-Acetyl-5-bromocotarnideneacetic acid.

This was prepared by heating bromocotarnine and excess of acetic anhydride to boiling for 10 minutes, diluting it with water and dissolving the precipitate which collected after 24 hours in dilute sodium carbonate and reprecipitating with acid. Crystallisation from dilute alcohol (charcoal) gave colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 211°. (Found: C, 48·51; H, 4·61. $C_{16}H_{18}O_6NBr$ requires C, 48·0; H, 4·50 per cent). The acid formed a white silver salt. (Found: Ag, 20·88. $C_{16}H_{17}O_6NBrAg$ requires Ag, 21·30 per cent).

5-Bromocotarnolactone.

Bromocotarnone (1 g.) was dissolved in acetone (3 c.c.), a solution of potassium carbonate (1 g. in 5 c.c. of water) added and the solution treated in the cold with powdered potassium permanganate (1·2 g.) added gradually during an hour. The bottle containing the mixture was shaken mechanically for 3 hours and after leaving overnight, the solution was filtered, the acetone removed on the water-bath, and the separating solid, mixed with brown oxides of manganese, was washed with a little sulphurous acid and crystallised from dilute alcohol (charcoal) as colourless crystals having a characteristic appearance of cut diamonds, m.p. 172°. (Found: C, 41·98; H, 3·24. $C_{11}H_9O_6Br$ requires C, 41·64; H, 2·83 per cent).

5-Bromocotarnic acid (2-methoxy-3:4-methylenedioxy-5-bromophthalic acid).

5-Bromocotarnolactone (0.5 g.) was dissolved in caustic soda (10%, 10 c.c.) by warming and a solution of potassium permanganate (0.6 g. in 20 c.c. of water) added drop by drop with vigorous shaking. The solution was filtered after an hour, sulphur dioxide passed and the clear, colourless solution was concentrated on the water-bath and left overnight. The crystalline powder which separated out was dissolved in cold sodium carbonate and was reprecipitated on adding acid. Crystallisation from dilute alcohol gave small colourless plates, m.p. 185°, yield 0.15 g. (Found: C, 37.69; H, 2.54. $C_{10}H_7O_7Br$ requires C, 37.61; H, 2.19 per cent). The *anhydride*, m.p. 225°, was obtained on heating the acid to 200° for a few minutes.

5-Bromohydrocotarnine.—Bromocotarnine (1 g.) was dissolved in *N*-HCl (20 c.c.) and 4% sodium amalgam added in small quantities at a time, the solution being kept acidic throughout the reduction. The clear solution was basified with strong caustic soda, extracted thrice with ether, dried over potassium carbonate and the ether removed on the water-bath. The yellowish oil which was left behind was rubbed with a few drops of HBr and the solid hydrobromide collected and washed with a little cold water; the free base was liberated with caustic soda and crystallised first from ether and then from a mixture of benzene and petroleum as colourless plates, m.p. 80° (Wright records m.p. 76°), yield 0.6 g. The same product was obtained also in good yield by brominating hydrocotarnine in acid solution by Wright's method.

The *hydrobromide* is sparingly soluble and crystallises from hot water as colourless needles, m.p. 242°. [Found: Br (HBr), 20.99. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3NBr$, HBr requires Br (HBr), 20.90 per cent].

The *perbromide hydrobromide*, prepared in the usual manner, crystallises from alcohol in orange coloured plates, m.p. 166° (decomp.). The available bromine was estimated by the method described before. [Found: Br, 29.34. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3N Br_2 \cdot HBr$ requires Br (available), 29.57 per cent].

Attempts to obtain bromocotarnine from the above by leaving it in contact with water or by warming a suspension of the substance in water were unsuccessful. In every case reduction of the solution with H_2S in the usual way yielded only the unchanged bromo-hydrocotarnine.

5-Bromonarceine.

A mixture of 5-bromonarceine (5 g.) and methyl-*p*-toluene sulphate (4 g.) was heated on a boiling water-bath for 45 minutes and then for half an hour in a glycerol-bath at 110° - 120° . The syrupy liquid was made slightly alkaline with caustic soda and steam passed in for 2 hours. The dark coloured solid which separated out of the solution after 12 hours was collected and purified by dissolving in hot alcohol (charcoal) and adding water till it was permanently turbid. The precipitate was collected after 12 hours and crystallised twice from boiling water which deposited rosettes of soft colourless needles, m.p. 193° , yield 2.7 g. It dissolves readily in alcohol and most of the common organic solvents; it is sparingly soluble in water. It forms sparingly soluble salts with the mineral acids. The material did not lose weight on drying at 100° in vacuum. (Found: C, 52.23; H, 5.10. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{NBr}$ requires C, 52.67; H, 4.96 per cent).

The *hydrochloride* crystallises in clusters of needles, m.p. 241° , even from dilute solutions. It suffered no loss of weight on drying at 110° over P_2O_5 in vacuum (Found: Cl, 6.01. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{NBr}, \text{HCl}$ requires Cl, 6.33 per cent).

The *hydrobromide* crystallises from hot water in needles, m.p. 225° . [Found: Br(HBr), 13.05. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{NBr}, \text{HBr}$ requires Br (HBr), 13.22 per cent].

The *picrate* crystallises from alcohol in bright yellow plates, m.p. 153° .

The *platinichloride* separated out as pale yellow prisms, m.p. 198° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 13·29. (C₂₃H₂₆O₈NBr, HCl) PtCl₄ requires Pt, 13·38 per cent].

The *methyl ester* was prepared by saturating a suspension of bromonarceine (1 g.) in cold methanol (10 c.c.) with dry HCl, standing for 12 hours and then diluting it with water and making alkaline with sodium carbonate. The precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless plates, m.p. 114°. (Found: C, 53·37; H, 5·61. C₂₄H₂₈O₈NBr requires C, 53·53; H, 5·2 per cent).

PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
MADRAS.

Received April 11, 1935.

Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and β -Ketonic Esters. Part III. Use of Various Condensing Agents.

By DUHKHAHARAN CHAKRAVARTI.

In the condensation of various mono-, di- and trihydric phenols with β -ketonic esters it has been observed that coumarins are produced using sulphuric acid as the condensing agent but phosphorus pentoxide may produce either coumarins or chromones (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407, 619; 1932, 9, 25, 31, 389; cf. Robertson and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1256, 1877, 2426; 1932, 1180, 1681). Excepting in the case of condensation of β -naphthol with unsubstituted acetoacetic ester (Dey and Lakshminarayanan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 153) no other case has been detected where a chromone is formed even in traces using sulphuric acid. Attention was, therefore, directed towards the investigation of the part played by phosphorus pentoxide in the formation of chromones as well as towards the possibility of substituting any other condensing agent for phosphorus pentoxide for the synthesis of chromones. Thus various acidic, basic and neutral condensing agents like phosphoric acid, zinc chloride, hydrochloric acid gas, sodium ethoxide, boric anhydride and sodium acetate have been tried. Zinc chloride and hydrochloric acid gas were previously used by investigators in Pechmann's reaction for the synthesis of coumarins. It is remarkable to note that if condensation takes